

Deliverable 8.3: Video Presentation

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Owner

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Context

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is genuinely a result of the Hiperdias project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Version	Summary of Change	Written By	Approver	Date
0.1	First draft	Julie Devall	Marwan Abdou-Ahmed	16/12/2016
0.2	Update to links, minor formatting amendments	Julie Devall & Emma Bowden		06/01/17
1.0	Updates to screenshots	Julie Devall & Emma Bowden	Marwan Abdou-Ahmed	16/01/17

2 **Scope**

This document should provide an overview about the prerequisite of the initial Video Presentation for the Hiperdias Project and its availability.

3 **Reasons for delay**

This deliverable was due in M4 of the project; it is being submitted in M12. It was felt by the consortium, in M4, that there was insufficient project output at that time to produce a video of interest. The Project Officer was informed. Since then, there were unanticipated difficulties in obtaining permission from the relevant persons within some beneficiary organisations to publish the imagery used. The video has now been approved by all partner beneficiaries and published.

4 **Hiperdias Video Presentation**

It was decided across the consortium that an initial video would highlight the following:

- Project name and logo
- The 3 main applications of the Hiperdias Project
- Focus on the “end-user” applications of Hiperdias within the project
- Highlight the benefits of the Hiperdias Laser
- Explain that Hiperdias is an EU funded project
- Highlight the partner organizations across Europe
- Provide links to the Hiperdias Website and other social media links
- Display the Photonics21 logo as stated in the Grant Agreement for dissemination

4.1 Project Name and Logo

The first frame of the video introduces the Hiperdias Brand Logo.

4.2 Setting the context of why lasers are important in society

The laser technology market is estimated to be worth approximately 14 billion euros by 2020

There is an increasing demand for high speed lower powered lasers that can work on a micro scale

Some of the most important forms of technology we use today could not have been made without using lasers

Lasers are used in the medical industry today;

1. Procedures (i.e. surgery)
2. Fine micro-instruments made by using lasers

4.3 Providing a brief explanation of the three main applications

4.4 Explaining the benefits of the Hiperdias Laser

Application 1: Diamond Polishing = The Hiperdias Laser will replace mechanical process of diamond polishing. A “mirror finish” to the diamond will be achievable. (E6)

Application 2: Fine Cutting of Metals = Even more intricate cutting than is currently possible will be achieved. (C4L)

Application 3: 3D Silicon Processing = The Hiperdias Laser will achieve a 10 times increase in ablation rate than what is currently possible. (BOSCH)

4.5 Highlighting European Project Funding

4.6 Highlighting the partners

4.7 Project Funding and EU Grant informations with EU Logo and Photonics21 Logo

5 Video Availability

The video is available on the;

- Official Hiperdias Website www.hiperdias.eu
- Hiperdias YouTube Channel [Link to Hiperdias video on Youtube](#)
- Hiperdias Twitter Account <https://twitter.com/hiperdias>